
Corrosion Inhibition of Mild Steel using *Parinari polyandra* Leave Extracts in Dilute Hydrochloric acids

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Abstract Metallic materials remain indispensable companion in industries. The study is aimed at assessment of inhibition properties of *Parinari polyandra* leaves on mild steel in 1 M HCl solution. This was investigated using gravimetric and electrochemical methods. Physicochemical and spectroscopic analyses of the leave extract were done using standard methods. A yield of 19.82% was obtained while FTIR spectra of leave extract showed bands of 3404 cm⁻¹ and 2926 cm⁻¹ which indicated the presence of strong band of phenolic O-H, and C-H stretch functional groups respectively. A maximum inhibition efficiency of 97.22% against corrosion was obtained. Langmuir adsorption fitted the inhibitor data well. From electrochemical methods, corrosion rate value of 17.626 mmpy obtained for uninhibited mild steel was higher than values of 0.02044 – 2.2267 mmpy range recorded for mild steel surface covered with *P. polyandra* leaves extract in acidic medium. SEM images showed inhibition effect of leave extract against corrosion of the mild steel in 1 M HCl solution. Electrochemical analysis using Tafel plot also showed the leave extract inhibition capacity suggesting a mixed type inhibitor. Thus, *P. polyandra* leave extract might act as green inhibitor for mild steel utilized in industrial applications.

Keywords Corrosion, *Parinari polyandra*, Weight Loss studies, Adsorption Isotherm, FTIR, SEM, Thermodynamics and Tafel Plot.

1. Introduction

Corrosion process is a naturally occurring phenomenon which affects our society daily and results into damage, destruction and degradation of household gadgets, automobiles, airplanes, highway bridges, military armoured and petrol tanks among others. High-impurity products can be exploited during the exploitation of crude oil which might enhance corrosion. In the case of oil and gas wells and pipelines, corrosive products like carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), and free water can cause corrosion to these wells and pipelines [1].

Continual extraction of CO₂, H₂S, and free water through oil and gas components can damage the inner surface of oil and gas wells and pipelines. This material degradation results in the loss of mechanical properties like strength, ductility, impact strength, and so on, which leads to loss of materials, reduction in thickness, and at times ultimate

failure. If the degradation continues, the component may completely break down and would require replacement. The serious consequences of the corrosion process have become a problem worldwide [2].

Successful developments of researches to obtain natural corrosion inhibitors are growing simultaneously as the demand for environmental protection has become necessary [3]. Many noticeable research works have been published with the aim of developing non-hazardous corrosion inhibitors referred to as “green” corrosion inhibitors [4,5]. Also, there has been increasing research in green plants, such as extracts of plants, essential oils and purified compounds to obtain non toxic and cheap corrosion inhibitors [6].

El-Etre, [7] investigated the inhibiting effect of *Baphia nitida* leaves extract as a good corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in 1 M H₂SO₄ while Lebe *et al.* [8] reported the effect of *Euphorbia hirta* and *Dialium guineense* leave extracts on the corrosion of aluminium in 0.25M NaOH. It has been shown that there is influence of *Daucus carota* aerial part extract against effect of corrosion on mild steel in 1 M hydrochloric acid solution [9].

The possible application of *Pentaclethra macrophylla* Bentham leave extracts as a corrosion inhibitor as well as inhibitive effect of the natural onions juice extract of khillah (*Ammi visnaga*) against zinc corrosion has been investigated [10,11]. The inhibition efficacy of *Punica granatum* extract on brass in acid media and that of essential oil from fennel *Foeniculum vulgare* against carbon has been investigated [12,13]. Obot *et al.*, [14] studied the corrosion inhibition efficiency of *Ipomoea involcrata* leaf extract on aluminium. The corrosion properties of *Raphia hookeri* gum—halide mixtures and inhibition of mild steel in alkaline medium using polyvinyl alcohol has been studied [15].

However, there has been little study on corrosion effect of *Parinari polyandra* with exception of its leave extract on inhibitory activity against corrosion of mild steel in sulphuric acid solution which is not detailed [16]. Therefore, this study emphasized on detailed investigation of inhibitory effect of *Parinari polyandra* leave extract using weight loss and electrochemical techniques as well as study of its kinetics, thermodynamics and adsorption isotherms of *P. polyandra* leaf extract onto mild steel surface in an acid medium.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of the corrosive solution and mild steel specimens

The corrosive solution used in this study is 1 M HCl solution and was prepared by measuring 86.0 ml (97 % purity of analytical grade) of the concentrated acid into a 1000 ml standard flask and made up to the mark with the deionized water.

Mild steel sheets were purchased from Iron Sheet merchant at Tanke Oke - Odo, Ilorin Kwara State, Nigeria. It was found to be of composition of (wt %): Fe (98.89 %), Ti (0.73%), Mn (0.20 %), Al 0.15%, P (0.011%), Mo (0.006%), W (0.0047%) and V (0.0024%) and were cut into the same size (2.5 x 2.0 x 0.85 cm). The Mild Steel sheets were separately polished mechanically with Sic emery papers of grade 200, 400 and 600 in successive sections and washed with deionized water, degreased with ethanol, dried in acetone and kept in moisture free desiccators prior to each experiment carried out [17].

2.2. Collection and Extraction of Plant Extract

Samples of *P. polyandra* leaves commonly known as *abeere in yoruba*, were obtained from University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria at latitude 8.4807° N and longitude 4.527° E coordinates. The leaves were identified at Herbarium in Department of Plant Biology, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. A 70.0 g of *P. polyandra* leaves were washed, dried, grounded and soaked in a 500 ml solution of ethanol (97% purity) for 48 h. After 48 h, the samples were filtered and filtrates obtained were further subjected to evaporation at 352 K in order to make it free of ethanol. The stock solutions of the extract was used to prepare different concentrations of the extract by dissolving 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 g of the extract in 1L of 1 M HCl for gravimetric analysis as well as electrochemical analysis [18]. The percentage yield of leaves extraction is calculated using the formula [19]:

$$\% \text{ yield of extraction} = \frac{M_1 - M_2}{M_1} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where M₁ is mass of the sample and the thimble before extraction,
M₂ is the mass of the sample and the thimble after extraction.

2.3. Determination of Physicochemical and Spectroscopic properties of *P. polyandra* leaf extracts

Physicochemical parameters such as yield (%), pH, conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), ash content (%), moisture content (%) and bulk density (g/ml) were determined using standard methods [5]. The Fourier Transform spectroscopic analysis of the *P. polyandra* leaf extracts was also done.

2.4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) Studies

Two cleaned mild steel specimen were immersed separately in 50 ml of blank (uninhibited 1M HCl) and inhibited 1 M HCl solutions with 0.2 g/L for 48 hours at room temperature (303 K), after which the mild steel sheets were removed and dried in air. The dried mild steel sheets were then subjected to scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using High vacuum Based SEM SCOTECH 30000 SEM (Germany) for visual physical surface morphology of steel sheets inhibited with *P. polyandra* leaf extract (inhibitor) and uninhibited sheets [10].

2.5. Measurement of corrosion effects using weight loss studies

Each pre-weighed mild Steel sheet was separately immersed in 50 ml each of different inhibitor leave extract concentrations (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 g/L) and in 50 ml of 1 M HCl solution without inhibitor (blank solution). The beakers were placed in a thermostated water bath [5]. The experiment was conducted at various temperatures of 303, 313, 323, 333 and 343 K for 10 hours each.

Corrosion rate (CR) and percentage corrosion inhibition efficiency were calculated using the equations 2 and 3:

$$CR(\text{gcm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}) = \frac{w}{At} \quad (2)$$

$$IE\% = \left(\frac{w_1 - w_2}{w_1} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where w , A and t are weight loss(mg), exposed area (cm^2) and minimum time (h) respectively while w_1 , w_2 indicate original weight of mild steel and also weight loss by mild steel in either uninhibited solution (blank) or inhibited solution (inhibitor solution of leave extract)

2.6. Measurement of corrosion effects using electrochemical studies

The electrochemical studies were performed using a VERSASTAT 400 complete dc voltammetry and corrosion system model with V3 Studio software. The mild steels were cut into 1 cm^2 square area and the area was exposed to the corrosive media with and without inhibitors as a working electrode and Ag/AgCl rod as counter electrode. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as reference electrode and was connected by a Luggin's capillary. The experiments were undertaken at a room temperature (303K). The working electrode was immersed in a test solution for one hour until a stable open circuit potential was attained. The Tafel analysis study was set from cathodic potential of -250 mV to anodic potential of +250 mV with respect to the corrosion potential at a sweep rate of 1 mV/s. The linear Tafel segments of the anodic and cathodic curves were extrapolated to corrosion potential to obtain the corrosion current densities (i_{corr}). Each experiment was carried out three times to estimate reproducibility and average values of the electrochemical parameters are reported [20].

3. Results and Discussion

Yield is regarded as the quantity of product formed per the quantity of starting materials. From Table 1, it can be observed that yield of *Parinari Polyandra* leaves extract was found to be 19.82 %, and its pH is 4.8.

Table 1: Physicochemical Properties of Leaves (Raw), and Leaves Extracts of *Parinari polyandra*

Physicochemical Properties	Raw Leaf	Leaf Extract
Yield (%)	----	19.82
pH	5.3	4.8
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	714.19	431.24
Ash Content (%)	6.34	7.21
Moisture Content (%)	14.53	12.45
Bulk Density (g/ml)	0.32	0.41

---- indicates not applicable; percentage error for each parameter is less than 5%

The inorganic mineral content of the *P. polyandra* leaves extract which represents the ash content was found to be 7.21% while its moisture content was 12.45%. The conductivity of its leave extract obtained was 431.24 ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) and its bulk density was found to be 0.41(g/ml). It could also be observed that pH of raw leaves is comparable to its leave extract as both fell within acidic region of 5.3 and 4.8 respectively. All values of various parameters of raw leaf were found to be higher than its corresponding extracts with exception of ash content and bulk density whereby leaf extract was found to be greater in value. The increase in ash content might be due to chemical reagents used during treatment of the leave extract with chemical reagents that might have contributed to the minerals.

3.1. FTIR Analysis

The micrograph of the FTIR analysis of the leave extract of *P. polyandra* is shown in Figure 1 while the assignment of important bands of this leave extract is presented in Table 2. Strong band of 3404 (cm^{-1}) was discovered and it was assigned to Phenolic OH stretching vibration which is attributed to the presence of phenolic groups involved in hydrogen bond. The bands 2924 (cm^{-1}) was assigned to C-H stretching vibrations of methoxyl group in *Parinari polyandra* leaves extract.

At band 1444 (cm^{-1}) OH bend in carboxylic acid was observed in *Parinari polyandra* leaves extract. As regarding band at 1342 (cm^{-1}), it revealed the C-C stretch of ketones in *P. polyandra* leaves extract. Bands at 1203 (cm^{-1}) and 1220 (cm^{-1}), are assigned to the C-C (O)-C stretch of esters in bonds in aliphatic ethers stretching vibrations of *P. polyandra* leaves extracts. As regarding the absorption bands in the 833 (cm^{-1}) – 555 (cm^{-1}) indicate the hetero-atoms present in the *P. polyandra* leaves extracts.

Figure 1: FTIR Spectrum of Parinary Polyandra leaves extracts

Table 2: Assignment of the important peaks observed in the leaves extracts of *Parinari polyandra*

Absorption band location (cm^{-1}) of <i>P. polyandra</i> leaves	Types of vibration and Assignments
3404	Stretching vibration of Phenolic OH group
2926	C-H stretching vibration of methoxyl group
1612	C=C Ring stretch(conjugated) in Aromatic compounds
1444	O-H bend of carboxylic acids
1342	C-C stretch in ketones
1203	C-C (O)-C stretch of esters
833	C – hetero-atoms vibration.
800	
555	

3.2. Corrosion Studies

Corrosion study involves the study of extent of loss material of a given metal when exposed to a certain harsh conditions. Although gravimetric method is not a very reliable method and is time consuming and it cannot predict the mechanism of a corrosion reaction effectively. Corrosion measurement could also be carried out using electrochemical techniques [19].

Table 3 indicates the various data obtained from the gravimetric method of weight loss of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution of uninhibited as well as inhibited solution with different concentrations of inhibitors at different temperatures.

The corrosion rate was found to decrease as the concentration of *P. polyandra* leaves extract (inhibitor) increases. For temperature of 303 K, when mild steel was inhibited with various concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaf extract, it caused the corrosion rate to decrease from 0.0195 to 0.0182 $\text{gcm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ when the concentration of the inhibitor increased from 0.1 g/L to 0.5g/L respectively in line with result obtained in literature [20].

It was observed from the plots of corrosion rate of mild steel in 1 M HCl against the concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaves extract as an inhibitor that the corrosion rate of mild steel decreased with progressive increase in the concentration of the inhibitor and this was seen to be most evident at the highest temperature of 343 K (Figure 2). Akpan and Offiong [21] also reported similar trend of result, when ciprofloxacin drug was used as an eco-friendly inhibitor.

Figure 2: Effect of *P. polyandra* leaves extracts (Inhibitor) concentration on corrosion rate of Mild Steel in 1 M HCl at various temperatures (303 – 343 K).

Also, the inhibition efficiency (I E) of the *P. polyandra* Leaves extracts ranged from 97.22 to 82.03% (Table 3). Inhibition efficiency (I E) increased gradually with rise in concentration of inhibitor but decreased with increase in the temperature. Maximum Inhibition efficiency of 97.22 % was obtained at 0.2 g/L of leaves extracts of *P. polyandra* inhibitor in 1 M HCl solution at temperature of 303 K. Similar trend has been reported in literature [22], when acetone extract of red onion skin was used as inhibitor of Zinc in 2M hydrochloric acid solution.

Table 3: Corrosion parameters of mild steel in 1 M HCl in various concentrations of leaves extract at different temperatures using weight loss technique

LEC(g/l)	W L(g)	Temperature (K)	C R ($\text{gcm}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$)	Θ	I E(%)
Uninhibited	1.1011	303 K	0.0404	N.A	N.A
0.1	0.4875		0.0195	0.09475	94.75
0.2	0.2646		0.0195	0.9722	97.22
0.3	0.4653		0.0186	0.9529	95.29
0.4	0.5788		0.0231	0.9404	94.06

0.5	0.4553		0.0182	0.9539	95.39
Uninhibited	1.4399	313 K	0.0575	N.A	N.A
0.1	0.9562		0.0382	0.8991	89.91
0.2	0.8546		0.0341	0.9192	91.92
0.3	0.7825		0.0313	0.9197	91.97
0.4	0.6439		0.0257	0.9317	93.17
0.5	0.5112		0.0204	0.9491	94.91
Uninhibited	1.6502	323 K	0.0600	N. A	N. A
0.1	1.1232		0.0449	0.8871	88.71
0.2	1.0056		0.0402	0.8929	89.29
0.3	0.8481		0.0339	0.9104	91.04
0.4	0.7931		0.0317	0.9230	92.30
0.5	0.6215		0.0248	0.9430	94.30
Uninhibited	2.3215	333 K	0.0986	N. A	N. A
0.1	1.4312		0.0502	0.8585	85.85
0.2	1.2556		0.0502	0.8871	88.71
0.3	1.0563		0.0422	0.8920	89.20
0.4	0.9825		0.0393	0.9059	90.59
0.5	0.7784		0.0311	0.9219	92.19
Uninhibited	3.1358	343 K	0.1254	N. A	N.A
0.1	1.7842		0.0713	0.8203	82.03
0.2	1.6045		0.0642	0.8339	83.39
0.3	1.5213		0.0608	0.8404	84.04
0.4	1.3786		0.0551	0.8514	85.14
0.5	1.2015		0.0480	0.8780	87.80

LEC= Leaves extracts concentration, WL = Weight Loss, CR = Corrosion rate, θ = Degree of surface coverage, IE= Inhibition efficiency, NA = Not applicable.

The variation of IE with *P. polyandra* leave extract inhibitor concentration at various temperatures that ranged from 303K to 333K is shown in Figure 3. It could be observed that as temperature increased, the effect of inhibition efficiency of *P. polyandra* leave extract on the mild steel decreased for the various concentrations investigated (Figure 3). This is because the tendency of molecules of leave extract to be attached to the surface of mild steel decreases with increase in temperature [22]. Figure 4 depicts the effect of corrosion rate on mild steel inhibited with various concentrations of *P. polyandra* leave extract at different temperature.

Figure 3: Effect of inhibitor (*P. polyandra* leaves extract) concentration on the inhibition efficiency of mild steel in 1 M HCl at temperature range of 303 – 343K.

Figure 4: Effect of Temperature on corrosion rate of mild steel in 1 M HCl inhibited with *Parinari polyandra* leaves extract solution at various temperature range of 303 – 343 K

3.3. Effect of Immersion Time

The effect of immersion time on corrosion rate (CR) and Inhibition efficiency (I E) in 1 M HCl corrosive environment is shown in Table 4. The corrosion rate (CR) and Inhibition efficiency (IE) were calculated using their respective formulae as at 3 days interval for total of 18 days in an uninhibited HCl and in the presence of maximum concentration of leaves extracts at room temperature. Corrosion parameters of mild steel in uninhibited 1 M HCl and with 0.5 g/L inhibited leaves extracts of *P. polyandra* at different immersion time at temperature 303 K, using weight loss techniques is presented in Table 4. From Table 4, it was observed that corrosion rate in uninhibited 1 M HCl increased from 0.052 g.cm⁻²h⁻¹ after 3 days of immersion to 0.584 g.cm⁻²h⁻¹ after 18 days of immersion.

Table 4: Effect of time of immersion on extent of corrosion of mild steel in un-inhibited and inhibited 1M HCl solution with various concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaf extract

Inhibitor Type	Immersion Time(days)	W L (g)		CR(g/cm ² h)		θ	I E (%)
		Uninhibited	Inhibited	Uninhibited	Inhibited		
Leaves Extract	3	0.132	0.103	0.052	0.020	0.9541	95.41
	6	0.190	0.168	0.076	0.045	0.9022	90.22
	9	0.256	0.205	0.145	0.057	0.8615	86.15
	12	0.297	0.278	0.295	0.075	0.8392	83.92
	15	0.300	0.295	0.304	0.109	0.8040	80.40
	18	0.350	0.325	0.584	0.250	0.7521	75.21

WL means weight loss; CR is corrosion rate, θ represents surface coverage and IE is inhibition efficiency. Temperature is at 303K

This trend also occurred when inhibited 1M HCl solution with leaves extract also followed the same trend but the rate of corrosion increase was obtained to be greatly reduced from 0.020 g.cm⁻²h⁻¹ after 3 days of immersion time to 0.250 g.cm⁻²h⁻¹ after 18 days of immersion time and this could be attributed to the presence of leaves extract that inhibited the corrosion rate.

Figure 5 showed the effect of immersion time on corrosion rate of mild steel immersed either in 1M HCl solution uninhibited or inhibited with 0.5 g/L leaves extract. It could be seen that the corrosion rate of mild steel was lowest with mild steel immersed in 1M HCl that contained 0.5 g/L *P. polyandra* leaf extract (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: Effect of Immersion time on corrosion rate of mild steel in 1M HCl solution uninhibited and inhibited with the 0.5 g/L leaves extracts solution

3.4. Adsorption Studies

Adsorption isotherms are very important in determining the mechanism of organo-electrochemical reaction. The inhibition of the corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl medium with addition of different concentrations of the *P. polyandra* leaf extract could be explained by the adsorption of the components of the plant extract on the metal surface. Inhibition Efficiency (%) is directly proportional to the fraction of the surface covered by the adsorbed molecule (θ). Therefore, the adsorption isotherm describes the relationship between the coverage of interface with the adsorbed species and the concentration of species in solution. The value of the surface

Coverage (θ) at different concentrations of the inhibitors in 1M HCl solution for the extract was made to fit into various adsorption isotherms.

3.5. Modified Langmuir adsorption isotherm for corrosion studies

Using this modified Langmuir expression shown in equation 4 [23]:

$$\frac{C_{inh}}{\theta} = \frac{m}{K_{ads}} + mC_{inh} \quad (4)$$

Langmuir plot of $\frac{C_{inh}}{\theta}$ against C_{inh} gave a straight lines for both *P. polyandra* leaf extracts inhibited 1M HCl solution. Figures 6 and 7 clearly showed that the adsorption of leaf extract onto mild steel surface fitted very well into modified Langmuir equation as the correlation coefficients for leaf extract of *P. polyandra* fell within the range of 0.998 – 0.999 at the different temperature range of 303 – 343 K. Table 5 summarizes the Langmuir parameters obtained.

Figure 6: Langmuir plot for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution inhibited with different concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaf extract at different temperatures

Figure 7: Langmuir plot for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution inhibited with different concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaves extract at two temperatures

Table 5: Langmuir parameters for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution inhibited with different concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaf extract at various temperatures

Temperature(K)	Leaf extract		
	K_{Lads} (g/L)	m	R^2
303	1.0499	1.051	0.999
313	1.0509	1.043	0.999
323	1.0669	1.059	0.999
333	1.0779	1.067	0.999
343	1.1350	1.124	0.998

K_{Lads} = Langmuir adsorption constant, m = a numerical value representing the slope.

It is known that K_{Lads} describes the adsorption strength of an inhibitor onto the mild steel surface [5]. The large values of K_{Lads} suggest efficient binding potential of the inhibitor onto the mild steel surface [24]. In this study, the value of K_L could be seen to slightly increase as the temperature rises from 303 to 343 K for the leaf extracts. The lowest K_{Lads} value obtained for leaf extract at 303 K was found to be 1.0499 g/L.

3.7. Temkin Adsorption

Temkin adsorption isotherm as applied to corrosion studies takes into account the interaction between adsorbent and adsorbate ions or molecules and it is based on the assumption that the free energy of sorption is a function of surface coverage [12]. The equation of Temkin adsorption isotherm is given as

$$\theta = 2.303K_T \log C \quad (5)$$

Where θ is the surface coverage, K_T is the Temkin adsorption constant and C is the inhibitor concentration. The Temkin plot for adsorption of inhibitor on the surface of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution at various temperatures were done by plotting surface coverage θ against $\log C$ (Fig. 8) and Temkin parameters are presented in Table 6.

Figure 8: Temkin plot for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution inhibited with different concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaf extract at various temperatures

The Temkin plots of θ versus $\log C_{inh}$ at various temperatures studied with leaf extract solution is depicted in Fig. 8. The graph is linear and the values of K_{Tads} increased as the temperature increased, while their coefficient of correlation of R^2 is in good range of 0.962 – 0.825 with exception of R^2 equal 0.024 (Table 8). A similar finding has been reported in literature [23,24].

Among the three corrosion adsorption isotherms investigated, Langmuir was found to be the best that fitted the corrosion adsorption data by the virtue of its higher value of correlation coefficient, R^2

Table 6: Temkin parameters for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution with different concentrations of *P. polyandra* leaves extracts at various temperatures

Leaf extract			
Temperature (K)	K_{Tads} (g/L)	m	R^2
303	0.9487	0.006	0.024
313	1.0163	0.063	0.894
323	1.0214	0.076	0.860
333	1.0218	0.083	0.962
343	0.9446	0.071	0.825

K_{Tads} = Temkin adsorption constant, m= a numerical value representing the slope.

Among the three corrosion adsorption isotherms investigated, Langmuir was found to be the best that fitted the corrosion adsorption data by the virtue of its higher value of correlation coefficient, R^2

3.8. Thermodynamic Studies

Thermodynamic properties such as Activation Energy (E_a), Enthalpy (ΔH), entropy of activation and (ΔS) show the mechanism of adsorption process involved. The values for (E_a), (ΔH) and (ΔS) gotten from this study are given in the Tables 7 and 8. The values were obtained from the Arrhenius plot of values of Log CR against $1/T$. The values of activation energy (E_a) decreased as the concentration increased. The (E_a) of an uninhibited solution was found to be 45.79 kJ/mol and raising the concentration of inhibitor from 0.1 g/L to 0.4 g/L led to reduction of E_a value of 45.79 kJ/mol to 8.97 kJ/mol at concentration of 0.4 g/L. The addition of higher concentration of leaf extract (inhibitor) produced a better and thicker protective film layer on the surface of the mild steel at a particular temperature. The trend of increase in the value of E_a as the concentration of inhibitors increase have been reported on various green plant extracts [25, 19].

Figure 9: Arrhenius plot for mild steel in uninhibited 1 M HCl solution

The values of Activation Energy (E_a), are used in this study to know the adsorption mechanism that takes place [26]. It was found that the constant or lower values (8.97 – 24.96 KJ/mol) of (E_a) in inhibited system compared to that of the blank solution (uninhibited) and as such indicate a chemisorption process of adsorption of inhibition. So, it is observed that optimum lowered E_a value of inhibited solution indicate the effectiveness of *P. polyandra* leave extract used as inhibitor and is comparable to values obtained in literature [5]. Therefore; the adsorption mechanism

might be suggested to be chemisorptions. The plot of $\log C_R$ against inverse of temperature of uninhibited solution produced a scattered graph with very low correlation coefficient R^2 (Fig. 9).

Figure 10a: Arrhenius plot for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution containing 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 g/L concentrations of *P. Polyandra* leaf extracts

Figure 10b: Arrhenius plot for mild steel in 1 M HCl solution containing 0.4 and 0.5 g/L concentrations of *P. Polyandra* leaves extracts

Table 7: Activation parameters of the dissolution of mild steel in uninhibited 1 M HCl and in the presence of different concentrations of leaves extracts

LEC (g/L)	E_a (kJ / mol)	R^2	ΔH (kJ / mol)	ΔS (j/mol K)	R^2
Uninhibited	45.79	0.341	70.61	-197.83	0.2169
0.1 g/L	24.92	0.9126	104.69	-146.95	0.9400
0.2 g/L	24.05	0.9565	108.59	-150.8	0.9300
0.3 g/L	23.08	0.9481	66.83	-153.90	0.7813
0.4 g/L	8.97	0.6335	57.69	-196.00	0.8841
0.5 g/L	24.96	0.8398	105.8	-199.00	0.9342

LEC = Leaves extract concentration, E_a = activation energy, ΔH = enthalpy of activation, ΔS = entropy of activation.

3.9. Kinetics Model

The corrosion reaction is a heterogeneous reaction which is composed of anodic and cathodic reactions at the same or different rate. It is on this basis that kinetic analysis of the data is considered necessary.

For first order kinetics,

$$r = -d \left(\frac{w_i - w_t}{dt} \right) = k_1 w_t \quad (6)$$

Where, w_i is the initial weight of the mild steel, w_t is the weight after time t , k_1 is the first order rate constant, which has a unit of h^{-1} .

Integrated first order is given as:

$$\ln(w_i - w_t) = -k_1 t + \ln w_i \quad (7)$$

Figure 11: First Order kinetic plot of weight loss of mild steel against immersion time in an uninhibited 1 M HCl solution

From the plot of $\ln(w_i - w_t)$ against t (hours) k_1 , was estimated as the slope, while intercept as $\ln w_i$. The rate constant was calculated from its slope as reported by the previous investigators [27]. The linear variation and slope k_1 which confirms a first order reaction kinetics with respect to the corrosion of mild steel in 1 M HCl solutions in the presence of the inhibitor. Figures 11 and 12 showed that the slopes of the plots have negative values and good correlation coefficients (R^2) with linear plots obtained which proofed that the reaction followed first order kinetic model in line with Eddy *et al.*, [28] findings that investigated the effectiveness of ethanol extract of mango peel waste for corrosion inhibitor of the mild steel.

Figure 12: First Order kinetic plot of weight loss of mild steel against immersion time in various concentration of *P. polyandra* leaves extracts in 1 M HCl solution.

3.10. Electrochemical Studies

Electrochemical method of corrosion studies is the most reliable method to give information about the mechanism of a corrosion process and it is not a time consuming method unlike the gravimetric method. Table 8 shows the electrochemical parameters obtained from the electrochemical studies of *Parinary polyandra* leaves as corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution [29].

Table 8: Electrochemical parameters obtained from the electrochemical studies of *Parinary polyandra* leaves extracts

Inhibitor concentration (g/L)	E_{corr} (mv)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	β_a	β_c	C.R (mmpy)	I E (%)	Chi square
Uninhibited	-479.23	-1.518	153.28	102.04	17.63	NA	52.87
0.1 g/L	-627.11	-191.90	54.89	756.44	2.23	79.90	61.13
0.3 g/L	-589.45	-13.13	328.72	1.565	0.15	88.49	195.72
0.5 g/L	-558	-1.76	92.737	156.29	0.02	95.34	195.72

Electrochemical studies of corrosion inhibition of mild steel using *Parinary polyandra* leaves extract by Tafel electrochemical analysis gave various values of corrosion parameters for different inhibitor concentration. Tables 8 revealed that the leaf extract inhibitor altered the Anodic beta (β_a) values from 153.23 obtained from uninhibited solution and Cathodic beta (β_c) value (102.04) obtained from anodic beta of the system and thus the inhibitor acted as a mixed inhibitor [30].

From Table 8, it could be seen that the corrosion rate decreased from the uninhibited system 17.63 (mmpy), 2.23 (mmpy) at concentration 0.1g/L to 0.020 mmpy at concentration 0.5 g/L where leaf extracts are used as inhibitor significantly, as the concentration of the inhibitor. Figure 13 represents the Tafel plot of isolated Leaves extract as corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution

Figure 13: The Tafel plot of isolated Leaves extract as corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in 1 M HCl solution

3.11. Scanning Electron Microscopy Analysis (SEM)

Figure 13: SEM micrograph of Mild Steel of uninhibited 1 M HCl solution after 48 hours of immersion at magnification of 500X

Scanning electron microscopy analytical technique revealed the visual physical morphological changes on the surface of Mild Steel that were separately immersed in uninhibited 1 M HCl solutions and in the inhibited HCl containing different concentrations of *Parinary polyandra* leaves extract. SEM images for mild steel immersed in uninhibited 1 M HCl solution and in the presence of 0.5 g/L of inhibitors of leaves extracts for 48 hours at 303 K are shown in Figures 13 and 14. The images revealed that in the absence of inhibitor, cracks resulted from corrosion attack on the surface of mild steel in an uninhibited medium while the cracks and corroded areas were reduced in the SEM images of the mild steel inhibited with various leaves extract concentrations. This is due to formation of protective layers by the molecules of inhibitors inhibiting the corrosion of the mild steel [5].

The image in figure 13 shows many cracks due to corrosion attack on the surface of the mild steel [10].

Figure 14: SEM micrograph of Mild Steel in inhibited 1 M HCl containing 0.5 g/L of leaves extracts after 48 hours of immersion at magnification of 500X

The image (figure 14) revealed no obviously crack occurrences. This is due to the presence of leaves extract inhibitor adsorbed on the surface of mild steel, thus it prevented the mild steel from corrosion attack [5, 10].

Conclusion

In conclusion, ethanoic leave extract of *Parinary polyandra* exhibited good inhibiting characteristics against corrosion of mild steel in 1M HCl solution. This might be due to presence of carbonyl and hydroxyl groups in the leaves extract that served as adsorption site onto the mild steel surface. SEM analysis also confirmed the corrosion of inhibition mild steel in 1M HCl solution compared to high inhibition potential of *P. polyandra* leaves extract. Both gravimetric and electrochemical methods showed that inhibition efficiency of the leave extract decreased with increase in the temperature and increased with increase in immersion period of mild steel in leaves extract. Langmuir adsorption isotherm best described the adsorption of leaves extract onto the mild steel surface and it followed endothermic process. The first order kinetics also favored the adsorption process of *P. polyandra* leaves extract onto the mild steel.

Disclosure statement

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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